

HISTORY OF THE STUDY APPROACHES OF KINSHIP TERMS

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Abstract

Modern linguistics is increasingly paying attention to the comparative analysis of languages, which is a natural phenomenon: the rapid process of realizing one's own identity, cultural identity, covering many peoples, is unique in the development of humanities. manifested itself. First of all, the attention of the public mind was focused on directions and networks that allow to fill or develop the idea of the specific characteristics of the national road within the framework of the general direction of civilization, and to determine its value. to directions specific to their culture, language, that is, national mentality.

Key words

Kinship terms, phenomenon, comparative analysis, synchronic, diachronic

Annotation

The analysis of modern language is paying more attention to languages, this is a natural event: the rapid process of realizing one's own identity, cultural identity, which has attracted many peoples, is manifested in a unique way in the development of humanities. lady it has been. First of all, it was focused on filling or developing the idea of significant national changes in the general direction of civilization, improving its value. culture, the uniqueness of the language, that is, to the directions characteristic of the national mentality.

Key words

Kinship terms, phenomenon, comparative analysis, synchronic, diachronic

As a linguistic unit, a word is related to an object or phenomenon of the real world. In different cultures, not only objects or events, but also cultural ideas about them can be different. After all, they live and work in different worlds and cultures [Sadokhin 2004: 163]. In other words, language not only reflects the world, but also constructs an ideal world in our minds.

Among the thematic layers of the dictionary, the dictionary layer representing family relations takes one of the first places in terms of origin and great stability of the concepts defined by them. Such words are often used to confirm certain conclusions of the authors of various works [Butinov 1979; Gak 1997; Zelenetsky 1983; Kazantsev 2004; Fedorchuk 2001], devoted to issues of comparative study of

related languages and basic vocabulary. However, the history of their forms and meanings, stylistic functions, distribution, derivational potential, etc. in a given European language have not been sufficiently studied.

Of particular interest is the group of words that serve to express kinship relations between people in the language of any nation - these are kinship terms [Kryukov 1972]. At the same time, it should be clarified that the word in this phrase is not used "not in the sense strictly assigned to this concept, but in the sense that is characterized by ambiguity and the absence of a special emotional color" [Isachenko 1962: 24].) it is easy to find those that have several options for their meanings (for example, bride). However, in linguistics, the word "term" is often used in different and often ambiguous meanings. Thus, according to a long-established tradition, they also talk about kinship terms [Kapanadze 1965: 75].

In every culture, kinship terms refer to a vocabulary that is historically, genetically, and culturally one of the oldest. The establishment of kinship relations goes in parallel with the formation and development of society.

It is impossible not to recognize that the structuring principles of the kinship system depend on real social relations. Certain social institutions are reflected in the terminology of kinship, and as a result, it can serve as a source for studying the social structure of society. Analysis of the development of kinship systems thus sheds light on the general and specific laws of the historical evolution of society [Schweitzer 1978: 145].

We first set out to describe the system of nominations included in the dictionary, and then we consider the manifestation of the studied language as a cultural practice, i.e. as a communication system in which intrapsychic and interpsychic phenomena are repeated, forming and forming the social structure of society, its cultural structure. In our work, we aim to conduct an ethnographically based description of linguistic contact using the terms kinship and property. Such a definition is carried out from the point of view of linguistic anthropology, which is concerned with "understanding language as a set of signs that make up the social structure of society, woven together individual and social images of real or possible worlds" [Makarov. 2006: 36]. Thus, the typical "speaker" and "listener" act primarily as subjects in their social roles, belonging to complex social institutions, embedded in large-scale networks of communication, interrelated expectations. , has a set of ideas, values".

To develop a typology of kinship systems, we chose the path of synchro-comparative study of languages, which will probably remain among the leaders in the near future. We then identified kinship systems that exist in different language

cultures and are available for direct observation. This method allowed us to cover a wide range of factual material.

A combination of these two main methods seems to produce the greatest results. And from this point of view, on the one hand, systems that exist for ethnographic study in their current state, and on the other hand, have written sources from a much longer period of their history, are of great importance.

Among existing works of a comparative-typological nature, the main place is occupied by studies devoted to the analysis of grammatical (morphological, syntactic) or phonetic phenomena. The field of lexical semantics is still not well studied. "It seems that the most favorable conditions for research in the field of vocabulary can arise, because to some extent all compilers of bilingual dictionaries have to think about the similar and different shades of the listed words. "However, the strange thing is that in the field of contrastive lexicology, the main advances in theory are not felt" (Yartseva 1981).

This situation is explained by the uniqueness of the studied material. In comparative typological analysis, structural phenomena are compared. It should be noted that although the issue of coherence in the lexical-semantic field of language is being discussed, it is still controversial. The famous thesis about the infinity and incalculability of lexical-semantic level units, the mobility of the language dictionary is regularly repeated throughout the history of the development of linguistics. These features of the dictionary are an obstacle, and the researcher is surprised every time he begins to examine the vocabulary of a language in order to determine the systematic organization of its elements.

Success in the study of the semantic side of words largely depends on the success of researchers in establishing connections and relationships between the elements of the lexical-semantic level of the language, which are relatively easy to determine in the analysis of grammatical or phonological phenomena. The lack of a complete systematic description of such an important area of the language as the vocabulary can be a serious obstacle in the typological comparison of individual language systems and languages in general, because it requires a preliminary analysis that covers all levels equally.

The relevance of our etymological analysis of kinship terms as the oldest layer of the vocabulary related to the development of the family and its forms is determined, first of all, by the fact that it allows us to determine a specific feature. the most important concepts for the languages under consideration. In addition, the study of the nomenclature of kinship terms makes it possible to draw a number of

conclusions about the genetic relationship of languages, to comprehensively describe the lexical-semantic systems of languages.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is the work carried out by several local and foreign linguists on the kinship terms in the world languages and various aspects of the languages we study, and the results in it are not specialized in the language, but in the language for a certain work, activity or purpose. can be used to teach languages to students.

CONCLUSION

Using the universal principles of classification based on the analysis of the features of the kinship nomenclature systems in Chinese and Uzbek languages, diachronic and synchro-comparative analysis of kinship terms. taking into account regional characteristics using the comparative analysis of cultural and linguistic concepts of kinship terms in the material of different language cultures. General and specific features of the cultural characteristics of kinship terms in these languages are determined.

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